

Title: An Introduction To Decentralization, Markets and Trade

Name: Adrian Brathwaite

Affiliation: SellBloc Inc., Toronto, Canada

INTRODUCTION:

SellBloc is a decentralized autonomous business development network on the Blockchain

AIM:

To disrupt trade by removing the middle man. This allows for peer to peer interaction between business entities globally.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

A blockchain is a decentralized and distributed digital ledger that is used to record transactions across many computers so that the record cannot be altered retroactively without the alteration of all subsequent blocks and the collusion of the network. Two parties are able to make an exchange without the oversight or intermediation of a third party, strongly reducing or even eliminating counterparty risk.

RESULTS:

My dream is such that a cocoa farmer in Ghana can benefit in producing and selling directly to a small manufacturer in Detroit or anywhere of his or her choosing with autonomy. This not only benefits both parties but provides products to the consumer at near costs access with total transparency ,self determination and freedom.

CONCLUSIONS:

Products move freely between companies without centrist control with Freedom of Choice.

KEYWORDS:

Smart Contracts, Blockchain, bitcoin, Ethereum, crypto, decentralization

BIOGRAPHY:

Adrian Brathwaite is a crypto trader, blockchain and fintech investor.

He has over 25 years of experience as a business development specialist and sales professional in Information technology, advertising, digital marketing and music.

He administers, strategizes and acquires new business for this unique management firm and private blockchain.

SellBloc is a decentralized autonomous organization(DAO) and business development network. We use the blockchain, along with Ethereum smart contracts technology, to assist Businesses secure unique peer 2 peer opportunities . We encourage democratic autonomy while utilizing economies of scale.

Our coming peer to peer network, gives access to savvy online processes like programmatic marketing, business development, big data, social media, branding and much more. Everything to run a modern business effectively in today's internet of things.